

The Pinene Content of Indian Turpentine.

BY

H. M. MULANY AND E. R. WASTON.

Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 573) reported that the lower boiling fraction in Indian turpentine obtained from *Pinus longifolia*, amounting to 47 or 60 per cent. of the turpentine, consists mainly of α - and β -pinene. On this authority we used the fraction of Indian turpentine boiling at 155-160° as a source of pinene, and after some time we came to doubt whether it does consist mainly of pinene: we subjected it to a further examination to settle this point. It did not give any solid pinene hydrochloride whilst a sample of pinene obtained from French turpentine gave a direct yield of 27.5 per cent. Oxidised by Baeyer's method with potassium permanganate it gave a product that did not crystallise even after it had been fractionated under reduced pressure. It gave no pinene picrate by Tilden and Forster's method (*J. Chem Soc.*, 1893, 63, 1388) or by a modification of this method, using molecular proportions of pinene and picric acid, whereas a sample of pinene obtained from British Drug Houses, Ltd., gave 16.6 per cent. of picrate by the modified method.

By Wallach's method (*Annalen*, 245, 251) it gave 1 per cent. of nitrosyl chloride whilst B. D. H. pinene gave a yield of 16.1 per cent. Oxidised by Henderson's method with mercury acetate (*J. Chem Soc.*, 1909, 95, 289) it gave only 1 per cent. of sobrerol whilst a sample of pinene fractionated from May and Baker's oil of terebinth gave 5.5 per cent. Heated in an autoclave

it gave no dipentene whilst the sample of pinene obtained from May and Baker's oil of terebinth under the same conditions (250-260° for 1 hour) gave 65 per cent. of dipentene which readily gave the tetrabromide. It gave no terpin hydrate by Wallach's method with alcoholic nitric acid or by shaking with dilute sulphuric acid whereas pinene from May and Baker's oil of terebinth gave a 60 per cent. yield of terpin hydrate with dilute sulphuric acid under the same conditions (shaking 10 g. with 190 g. water and 10 g. of sulphuric acid continuously for a week).

The conclusion is that this fraction of Indian turpentine contains very little pinene. It contains some Δ^3 -carnene as it gives the nitrosate, but the yield of the latter is not large. The product of oxidation by Baeyer's method gave an oxime melting at 121-2° whereas the oxidation product of pinene from foreign turpentine gave the oxime of *l*-pinonic acid, m.p. 131°.

The fraction boiling at 155-160° obtained from Indian turpentine is not large. One sample of first quality Bareilly turpentine gave 25 per cent. but another fresh sample gave only 8.6 per cent.

The final conclusion is that the pinene content of Indian turpentine must be very small.